

Title: Ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCHL1), beyond hydrolysis.

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Abbreviations:

UCHL1	Ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase L1
PD	Parkinson's disease
AD	Alzheimer's disease
UPS	Ubiquitin-Proteasome system
DUB	Deubiquitinating enzyme
UCH	Ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase
SUMO	small ubiquitin-like modifier
AMC	7-amino-4-methylcoumarin
IF	Immunofluorescence

Abstract:

Ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCHL1) is a component of the ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS) linked to neurodegeneration. Despite its exceptionally high abundance in neurons, UCHL1's precise role remains unclear. This review critically examines the proposed functions of UCHL1 and the challenges to understanding its role in neuronal cells. While UCHL1 hydrolyses small adducts from the C-terminus of ubiquitin, its occluded active site limits the range of possible substrates and restricts its activity as an efficient deubiquitinase (DUB). These constraints, alongside the paucity of identified substrates, challenge the centrality of this proposed role. We also explore the potential of UCHL1 acting as a ubiquitin ligase and its non-enzymatic role in stabilizing mono-ubiquitin by preventing its lysosomal degradation. By highlighting the unresolved complexities surrounding UCHL1, this perspective proposes several approaches to elucidate UCHL1's significance in the brain.

Introduction:

Ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCHL1) is an extensively studied enzyme, primarily due to its abundant levels in the brain¹. Mutations in the gene encoding for UCHL1 have been directly implicated in various neurodegenerative diseases. Notably, a mutation identified in a German family with Parkinson's disease (PD) results in an isoleucine-to-methionine substitution at position 93 (I93M) of UCHL1². Additionally, a mutation at position seven (E7A) is associated with an early-onset progressive neurodegenerative syndrome characterized by childhood-onset blindness³. Furthermore, several studies have demonstrated that lower levels and diminished enzymatic activity of UCHL1 are associated with Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathology across various research models⁴⁻⁶. Collectively, these findings emphasize UCHL1's role in maintaining neuronal integrity and function, defining it as a neuroprotective protein. Thus, preserving UCHL1 levels and activity may be crucial for mitigating the progression of neurodegenerative disorders.

Several years after its discovery as an abundant protein in neurons, UCHL1 was identified as a component of the ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS)⁷. This system serves as the primary mechanism for selective protein degradation in eukaryotic cells. The UPS operates in a highly complex and tightly regulated manner to maintain protein homeostasis and ensure proper cellular function⁸. Disruptions in protein clearance are linked to numerous diseases, including malignancies, autoimmune disorders, and neurodegenerative diseases⁹⁻¹¹. Protein degradation begins with substrate tagging by ubiquitin, a post-translational modification facilitated by a three-step enzymatic cascade. The sequential actions of the ubiquitin-activating enzyme (E1), the ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme (E2), and the ubiquitin ligase (E3) ultimately form a covalent isopeptide bond between the C-terminal glycine of ubiquitin and the ϵ -amino group of a lysine side chain on the substrate protein. This modification can be extended into polyubiquitin chains with various linkage types, depending on which lysine residue the distal ubiquitin unit is attached to⁸. The specific outcome of polyubiquitination depends on the type of lysine linkage; for example, K48-linked chains typically signal proteasomal degradation, whereas K63-linked chains are involved in non-degradative processes such as signaling and endocytosis¹². At the same time, the ubiquitin tag is recycled for further catalytic cycles by a diverse group of proteases known as deubiquitinating enzymes (DUBs)¹³. These enzymes are classified into seven subfamilies based on the sequence

UCHL1, beyond hydrolysis.

homology of their catalytic domain¹⁴. UCHL1 is one of only four members of the Ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase (UCH) subfamily. Most DUBs exhibit selectivity for specific ubiquitin linkages or cleavage sites within ubiquitin chains, whereas others display linkage promiscuity, targeting a wide range of ubiquitin configurations. Substrate recognition is often guided by additional domains that extend beyond the catalytic site¹⁵.

Although the UPS comprises the well-defined enzymatic activities mentioned above, not all of its components can be easily classified into one specific enzymatic category. A prominent example is UCHL1, which is nominally a DUB but also possesses additional activities. Based on sequence homology, UCHL1 belongs to the UCH subfamily of cysteine proteases⁷, which hydrolyze adducts from the C-terminus of ubiquitin to produce "ready for action" ubiquitin^{16,17}. Nevertheless, UCHL1 exhibits lower hydrolytic efficiency than other family members such as UCHL3 or UCHL5, and its unique three-dimensional structure restricts access to its active site limiting the diversity of its substrates^{16,17}. In fact, definitive hydrolysis substrates for UCHL1 have yet to be identified. Interestingly, UCHL1 exhibits an unusually high affinity for mono-ubiquitin¹⁸, implying product inhibition. These observations cast doubt on hydrolysis as its primary function and raise the potential of alternative roles.

Over the years, a range of activities beyond hydrolysis have been attributed to UCHL1. A notable study by Osaka H et al. (2003) proposed that UCHL1 might shield ubiquitin from lysosomal degradation through its high affinity for mono-ubiquitin effectively enhancing the intracellular half-life of ubiquitin¹⁹. Thus, UCHL1 contributes to the maintenance of the mono-ubiquitin pool through a non-enzymatic role. Another study conducted by Liu Y et al. (2002) proposed that UCHL1 may also function as a ubiquitin ligase²⁰. This study suggested that a dimeric form of UCHL1 could extend polyubiquitin chains on conjugated proteins such as α -synuclein²⁰. Chain elongation activity has occasionally been described as a distinct function within the UPS performed by distinct E4 enzymes²⁰. Could these intriguing findings suggest that UCHL1 exhibits dual antagonistic activities? Might UCHL1 serve as both a hydrolase and a ligase? And if so, what mechanisms determine whether UCHL1 acts as one enzyme or the other? The proposed ligase mechanism of UCHL1 lacks robust experimental evidence, leaving the observed ligation outcome open to interpretation. Moreover, subsequent studies have

been inconsistent in replicating the ubiquitin ligase activity^{3,4}, leading to skepticism within the research community^{21,22}.

In summary, UCHL1 possesses several biochemical activities; however, these are not well characterized and its biological function remains poorly understood. To date, none of these activities fully explain the exceptionally high levels of UCHL1 observed in neuronal cells. Here, we will delve into the ongoing dilemmas surrounding the proposed activities of UCHL1, placing particular emphasis on the contradictions and inconsistencies that have emerged over the years. Ironing out the underlying established and missing mechanisms will aid the interpretation of its biological function within neurons.

UCHL1 hydrolysis activity:

As a DUB, UCHL1 belongs to the UCH family, which also includes UCHL3, UCHL5, and BAP1¹³. These enzymes share a conserved catalytic core, known as the UCH domain, consisting of approximately 230 amino acids in a particularly knotted topology²³ (**Figure 1a, b**). This catalytic domain has two defining features: (1) a papain-like catalytic triad¹⁶, composed of a nucleophilic cysteine (Cys), and a general base/acid histidine (His) and aspartate (Asp) that enhance the nucleophilic properties of the thiol (**Figure 1b**). Together, the catalytic triad enables hydrolysis of a covalent bond at the C-terminus of ubiquitin; and (2) a distinctive active site cross-over loop, with a length that varies among UCH family members and plays a crucial role in determining substrate specificity¹⁶ (**Figure 1a, b**).

UCHL1 and UCHL3 are the smallest enzymes within the UCH family, as they consist solely of the UCH domain and lack the auxiliary domains present in BAP1 and UCHL5. They also possess the shortest active site cross-over loop, measuring 11 and 14 amino acids respectively. The tight crossover loop limits their hydrolytic activity to small adducts at the ubiquitin C-terminus¹⁶, considerably limiting their potential substrate repertoire. Due to the limited information available beyond their active sites, the small size and homologous structures of UCHL1 and UCHL3—characterized by their compact UCH domains and minimal active site cross-over loops—pose a significant challenge to researchers trying to elucidate their precise biological functions.

UCHL1, beyond hydrolysis.

The active site cross-over loop of UCHL3 covers the active site cleft with a diameter of approximately 12–15 Å²⁴, which is about half the diameter of the ubiquitin molecule (~25 Å)²⁵. This suggests that ubiquitin may be unable to pass under this loop, which could explain why UCHL3 is unable to cleave di-ubiquitin^{16,17}. However, the loop is flexible and can adopt alternative conformations that allow it to move aside²⁶. Therefore, despite the limited capacity to hydrolyze the iso-peptide bond between two ubiquitin molecules, UCHL3 has been documented to hydrolyze branched or longer peptides from the ubiquitin C-terminus of ubiquitin or a fusion protein formed from ubiquitin linked to the 60S ribosomal protein L40 encoded by one of the ubiquitin genes^{27,28}. In addition, UCHL3 can hydrolyze structured substrates, like the small ubiquitin-like modifier (SUMO) from the C-terminus of ubiquitin, with low efficiency^{29,30}. Importantly, cleavage of these complex substrates by UCHL3 has been observed *in vitro*, suggesting direct enzymatic action.

Unlike UCHL3, UCHL1 has been shown to cleave only a limited range of substrates, most of which are artificial³¹. This limited substrate repertoire is thought to result from its shorter crossover loop over the active site cleft with a diameter of approximately 10 Å³². Currently, there is no evidence suggesting that it possesses the flexibility required to accommodate or "thread" larger substrates, whether they are folded, extended, or unstructured adducts. Furthermore, the crystal structure of the UCHL1-Ub complex (PDB: 3KW5) reveals the rigidity of the loop, which results from interactions between specific residues in the crossover loop (Arg153, Asp155) and ubiquitin (Arg72, Arg74)³².

One of the unsolved issues regarding UCHL1 is the identity of its natural substrates. Given the aforementioned restricted access to the active site, what may be the cellular sources that provide suitable extended ubiquitin species as substrates? The importance of UCHL1 to neurons suggests that these substrates would be particularly critical in neuronal cells. Several potential sources have been proposed. First, an activated E1 or an E1~Ub (~ refers to thioester bond) intermediate complex. A nucleophilic attack by small nucleophiles, such as free thiols or amines, on the charged E1~Ub would result in C-terminally modified ubiquitin species³³. Second, ubiquitin precursors. Polyubiquitin fusions encoded by the UBB or UBC genes terminate in an extra amino acid at the C-terminus of the final ubiquitin unit²⁸. This small adage could be a substrate for hydrolysis by UCHL1. Third, is the proteasome. Incomplete proteasomal degradation or activity of proteasomal DUBs could yield ubiquitin fragments

with residual isopeptide-linked C-terminal extensions²¹. In all these scenarios, the potential role of UCHL1 would be to generate free ubiquitin with its characteristic GG C-terminus. Which would be an adequate substrate for activation by E1. By doing so, UCHL1 would act as a guardian of the active ubiquitin pool.

As a deubiquitinase, UCHL1 exhibits inherently lower hydrolysis efficiency than its paralog, UCHL3 (**Table 1**). One explanation is that, in the resting state, the catalytic triad of UCHL1 is arranged in an inactive conformation, which undergoes rearrangement upon ubiquitin binding¹⁸. This binding event induces a structural change that positions the key residues — the nucleophile (Cys90) and the general base (His161) — within approximately 4 Å of each other, aligning them in the configuration essential for catalytic activity (**Figure 2**)¹⁸. This alignment enables a transient proton transfer system between the side chains of cysteine and histidine. In papain-like proteases, this precise alignment is required, as the histidine residue acts as a general base, abstracting a proton from the cysteine thiol group and converting it into a more reactive nucleophile. The activated cysteine initiates hydrolysis of a properly positioned amide (peptide/isopeptide) bond at the C-terminus ubiquitin. In contrast, UCHL3 exhibits a pre-aligned catalytic triad that remains in the active conformation regardless of substrate binding²⁶. This structural readiness potentially allows UCHL3 a more immediate catalytic response, whereas UCHL1's activity is tightly regulated by the requirement of a conformational change upon substrate binding.

UCHL1 differs from UCHL3 not only in its slower substrate binding (due to the need for active site rearrangement), but also in its slower product release (Table 1). UCHL1 exhibits a particularly high affinity for its own hydrolysis product, free monoubiquitin^{18,19}. Slow product release attenuates the recycling of UCHL1, ultimately reducing the reaction turnover number (k_{cat})³⁴. For example, at saturation, UCHL1 hydrolyzes the artificial substrate, Ub-AMC, with a 200-fold lower rate constant (k_{cat}) than UCHL3²⁰. Since their K_m values do not differ by much, the catalytic efficiency of UCHL1 (k_{cat}/K_m) is lower too.

So far, no unique substrate has been identified for UCHL1; all documented substrates of UCHL1 can also be cleaved by UCHL3, and at an even faster rate. Is UCHL1 an inherently slow hydrolase, or have its preferred substrates simply not yet been identified? The distinct tissue distribution (UCHL1 is predominantly expressed in the brain, while UCHL3 is more widely distributed across various tissues) dictates that the search for its natural substrates should

UCHL1, beyond hydrolysis.

focus on neuronal tissue. Comprehensive mapping of C-terminally extended ubiquitin species across different cell types and tissues represents a critical first step in identifying potential substrates for UCHL1-mediated hydrolysis. Specialized mass spectrometry techniques would need to be developed to enrich and selectively detect C-terminal chemical modifications or non-native protein C-termini, similar to methods used for identifying protein N-termini, such as TAILS³⁵. Since it has a relatively high affinity for free ubiquitin, an overexpressed catalytically inactive UCHL1 mutant (with a substitution at Cys90) could be used as a trap for ubiquitinated peptides, facilitating the identification of potential substrates.

In contrast to the well-characterized structural and enzymatic properties of UCHL1 that dictate its activity toward small, unstructured ubiquitin adducts, *in vivo* studies associate UCHL1 with the deubiquitination of large, folded proteins. For instance, deubiquitylation of epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR)³⁶, NOXA³⁷, inhibitor of the NF- κ B transcription factor (I κ B- α)³⁸, and the alpha subunit of transcription factor hypoxia-inducible factor-1 (HIF1 α)³⁹, have been attributed to UCHL1 in specific cellular contexts. These findings are perplexing, as it is not easy to explain how these substrates gain access to the confined active site of UCHL1 without massive conformational changes or partnerships with additional factors. Typically, the specificity of DUBs is governed by substrate-recognition domains that lie outside the enzyme's catalytic core, which direct the enzyme to particular substrates, ubiquitin linkages, or cleavage sites. However, UCHL1 lacks such additional domains, making it difficult to explain how it achieves substrate specificity, particularly when dealing with structurally complex proteins. Moreover, none of these substrates are specifically neuronal, despite UCHL1 being most abundant in the brain, which leaves the enzyme's significance in neuronal tissue unexplained.

Ubiquitin stabilizer:

In enzymatic reactions, enzymes typically exhibit a low affinity for their product, facilitating their release and allowing efficient catalytic turnover. Accordingly, we anticipate that DUBs would show a low affinity for mono-ubiquitin. However, UCHL1 exhibits a relatively high affinity for its product, with a calculated dissociation constant (K_d) of ~ 200 nM for mono-ubiquitin,^{18,40}. Considering that free ubiquitin has been measured in tens of μ M, a K_d in the

sub- μ M range in cultured mammalian cells implies that UCHL1 is saturated with ubiquitin^{41,42}. Brain tissues are estimated to have even higher levels of free ubiquitin⁴¹, interestingly correlated with abundant UCHL1. This raises an important question: what is the functional advantage of UCHL1's high affinity for ubiquitin?

Several potential explanations for this high affinity are proposed: **An inherent enzymatic property.** End-product inhibition is a mechanism by which the product inhibits or controls the enzyme's function that helped make it⁴³. The affinity of UCHL1 for its likely substrates and product may be similar since they resemble each other (a ubiquitin molecule with small C-terminal adducts vs. a free mono-ubiquitin). **Protection of the key residue of Ubiquitin.** The active form of ubiquitin is defined by its C-terminus: a carboxyl group at Glycine 76. Once generated by the hydrolytic activity of UCHL1, the high affinity of free mono ubiquitin for UCHL1 may provide a benefit by protecting the carboxyl from modification or reduction in the cell until ubiquitin is relayed onwards to the E1 activating enzymes. **A ubiquitin buffering system.** UCHL1-bound ubiquitin may be a reservoir for an acute drop in ubiquitin levels, releasing free ready-for-action ubiquitin. **A ubiquitin delivery system.** Anchoring the ubiquitin molecule to a carrier (UCHL1 in this case) may facilitate its trafficking within the cell. This could be particularly significant in neurons, where precise regulation of ubiquitin distribution along axons is crucial for maintaining synaptic function and plasticity⁴⁴. This idea is supported by the observation that UCHL1 is highly expressed in projection neurons with long axons that extend to distant targets, rather than in local interneurons⁴⁵. **Modulating properties of UCHL1 itself.** A tight complex of UCHL1 and ubiquitin may serve as a scaffold for further protein-protein interactions.

Although numerous studies have examined the hydrolysis activity of UCHL1, few have explored the importance of its inherently high affinity for ubiquitin. One of the most frequently cited studies, conducted by Osaka H. et al. (2003), proposed that UCHL1's strong affinity for mono-ubiquitin in neuronal cells helps protect it from lysosomal degradation¹⁹. In this study, the researchers showed that Gracile Axonal Dystrophy (GAD) mice, which carry an in-frame deletion in exons 7 and 8 of the *Uchl1* gene, exhibit significantly reduced mono-ubiquitin levels. Additionally, overexpression of UCHL1 in cell culture prolonged the half-life of ubiquitin, likely by preventing its degradation within the lysosome as confirmed by using a

UCHL1, beyond hydrolysis.

lysosome inhibitor¹⁹. These findings highlight the critical role of UCHL1 in maintaining the cellular ubiquitin pool.

To determine whether hydrolysis is the responsible activity underlying these observations, the same team overexpressed both wild-type UCHL1 and the catalytically inactive C90A mutant in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells. A similar increase in ubiquitin levels was observed, by immunofluorescence, suggesting that UCHL1's hydrolytic activity is not critical for regulating the ubiquitin pool. This finding led to the hypothesis that the inherently high affinity of UCHL1 for ubiquitin might be the primary factor influencing ubiquitin stability. To test this hypothesis, a UCHL1 mutant (D30K) with a disrupted ubiquitin-binding site was overexpressed in the same cell line, leading to a smaller increase (than WT and C90A) in cellular ubiquitin levels. The authors concluded that the high affinity for ubiquitin is the property allowing UCHL1 to regulate the ubiquitin pool. It is important to note that this conclusion was based primarily on this single immunofluorescence (IF) experiment, which may not be sufficient to support such a critical claim. While there is no doubt of a correlation between UCHL1 and levels of free ubiquitin, the dynamic ubiquitin landscape and the rapid interchangeability between free and conjugated ubiquitin challenge the ability to pinpoint which form of ubiquitin is protected from degradation by UCHL1⁴². Employing advanced methodologies — beyond traditional approaches like Western blotting and immunofluorescence — could provide more precise quantification of mono-ubiquitin levels. For instance, overexpressed UCHL1 could serve as a free mono-ubiquitin sensor, or recombinant UCHL1 could serve to trap excess free mono-ubiquitin in the extract. It is also possible to isolate free monoubiquitin by selective precipitation⁴⁶ in order to evaluate the effect of UCHL1 levels on free mono-ubiquitin.

Moreover, structural studies, such as super-resolution or cryo-electron microscopy, could yield high-resolution views of UCHL1 in complex with ubiquitin and other proteins in the cell, offering valuable insights into the binding interactions and structural factors that may contribute to ubiquitin stabilization.

Ubiquitin ligation:

UCHL1 is a single-domain enzyme encasing a well-defined hydrolytic active site with a high affinity for ubiquitin. Thus, the same domain can explain the two aforementioned biochemical properties of UCHL1: a deubiquitinase and a ubiquitin stabilizer. A single study identified a third activity for UCHL1 - ubiquitin ligation. Using a C-terminally extended ubiquitin as a substrate, the enzyme successfully produced di-ubiquitin as a product²⁰. This function implies that UCHL1 can generate amide bonds at the C-terminus of ubiquitin beyond hydrolyzing them. The proposed ligation mechanism was described as being both dimerization-dependent and ATP-independent²⁰. At high concentrations, dimerization of UCHL1 could attribute a distinct role for the complex versus the monomer (**Figure 3**). As a dimer, one unit within the complex binds a donor ubiquitin modified at its C-terminus, while the other subunit binds an acceptor ubiquitin. After hydrolysis of the modification from the donor ubiquitin, the acyl-enzyme intermediate may react directly with the nucleophilic lysine of the acceptor ubiquitin rather than with water, producing di-ubiquitin²⁰. In this specific study, K63R mutant ubiquitin was unable to serve as an acceptor suggesting that UCHL1 facilitates the formation of K63 linkages. The authors proposed that UCHL1 can even extend polyubiquitin chains on specific substrate proteins as shown with α -synuclein²⁰.

The possibility of a dual-action enzyme is intriguing, encouraging multiple research groups to consider ligation as a significant function of UCHL1^{4,20,47,48}. While the proposed model involves multiple experimentally testable enzymatic steps, explicit validation of the mechanism has not been confirmed.

- 1) Dimerization Requirement:** The model posits that dimer formation is a prerequisite for UCHL1's ligase activity. Although some studies suggest UCHL1 can form dimers in solution, others dispute this claim³². Crucially, no direct evidence to date has demonstrated UCHL1 dimerization occurring within cells under physiological conditions.
- 2) Hydrolytic Dependence:** The model assumes that UCHL1's active cysteine residue is essential for its ligase activity. However, this could be readily tested using a catalytically inactive mutant (C90A). Surprisingly, such experiments have not been reported.

UCHL1, beyond hydrolysis.

- 3) Nature of the donor ubiquitin:** The experiment that directly measured ligase activity utilized ubiquitin modified at its C-terminus by 7-Amino-4-Methylcoumarin (Ub-AMC) as the donor ubiquitin. The aromatic coumarin ring of AMC can participate in electron delocalization with the adjacent amide bond, altering its resonance stability. This property likely destabilizes the amide bond, making the AMC a preferred leaving group compared to an amino acid. For AMC to reflect a biologically relevant leaving group, similar aromatic modifications of protein C-termini should naturally exist in cells.
- 4) The nature of the acceptor ubiquitin.** Free ubiquitin has been confirmed as a suitable ubiquitin acceptor for ligation, in agreement with the restricted access to the active site (**Figure 1b**). This prompts the question: How would the active site accommodate larger conjugates, such as ubiquitin- α -synuclein, for chain elongation ("E4-like activity") instead of generating free unanchored chains?

Moreover, no substrates have been conclusively validated as direct targets of UCHL1's proposed ligase activity to date. While some studies have speculated on potential substrates, including amyloid precursor protein (APP)⁴, α -synuclein²⁰, GRP78⁴⁸, and tubulin⁴⁷, these claims lack definitive experimental validation. What are the UCHL1 substrates under physiological conditions remains a significant gap in our understanding. Future research should prioritize identifying and validating substrates and binding partners of UCHL1 through advanced methods such as mass spectrometry-based ubiquitin profiling, *in vivo* ubiquitination assays, and structural studies to elucidate the underlying molecular mechanisms. Addressing these challenges will be essential to provide a clearer understanding of UCHL1's multifaceted roles in cellular biology, particularly within the nervous system.

Conclusions:

UCHL1 is defined as a DUB, yet, the source of extended ubiquitin species that could serve as substrates for hydrolysis is elusive. Another mystery surrounding UCHL1 is the ability to ligate ubiquitin. Elucidating the importance and mechanism of this activity and identifying targets would clarify the balance between these opposing activities.

A third property attributed to UCHL1 is its relatively high affinity for unconjugated ubiquitin. One example is an inactive variant of ubiquitin, UBB⁺¹, found in the brains of AD patients⁴⁹. UBB⁺¹ is a ubiquitin molecule that contains a 19-amino acid extension at the C-terminus. Although UCHL1 can bind UBB⁺¹⁴⁻⁶, it cannot process the extended tail⁵⁰. By competing with ubiquitin for binding to UCHL1, UBB⁺¹ may contribute to AD pathology. Indeed, over-expression of UCHL1 in a model system has been shown to suppress AD-like hallmarks associated with the accumulation of UBB⁺¹⁴⁻⁶.

The detailed biochemical characterization of UCHL1 over the last four decades still cannot fully explain the exceptionally high levels of UCHL1 observed in neuronal cells. Neither of its enzymatic activities is sufficiently unique to justify a dedicated enzyme unless there are distinct substrates that are yet to be discovered. Undoubtedly, UCHL1 binds and stabilizes unconjugated ubiquitin. Does this indicate that UCHL1 sequesters free ubiquitin, thereby shifting the balance to favor ubiquitin-independent degradation⁵¹? Alternatively, could UCHL1 provide a reservoir of ready-for-action mono-ubiquitin for cellular needs? Unlike other cell types, neurons exhibit long axonal transport, excitability, and an extended lifespan. They are particularly vulnerable to metabolic stresses due to their high energy consumption and susceptibility to oxidative damage. The need to quickly replenish ubiquitin for these activities may explain the importance of UCHL1 in the brain. The addiction of neurons to ubiquitin implies that inadequate replenishment or recycling of ubiquitin could contribute to neurodegeneration. We wish to promote the idea that coupling hydrolysis with ubiquitin-binding (**Figure 3, left**) may enable UCHL1 to perform quality control on the ubiquitin that it delivers to downstream clients, thereby explaining its neuroprotective role.

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UCHL1, beyond hydrolysis.

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	Feature	UCHL1	UCHL3	Reference
Substrate specificity	Loop length	11 amino acids	14 amino acids	16
	Cleft under the loop	~10Å	~12-15Å	24,32
	Evidence for loop flexibility	None	present	18,26
	Validated substrates	Very limited	Several substrates	27-30
Hydrolysis efficiency	Active conformation of the catalytic triad	Rearranges upon ubiquitin binding	Independent of ubiquitin binding	18,26
	Affinity for mono ubiquitin	Very high	High	34,40

Table 1. Comparison of UCHL1 and UCHL3 substrate specificity and hydrolysis efficiency.

Figure 1. Sequence and structure alignment of UCH subfamily members. a. Schematic representation of UCH sequences and alignment of the active site crossover loop. b. 3D structure alignment of UCH catalytic domains (in grey), highlighting differences in the crossover loops of UCHL1(PDB: 3WK5, green), UCHL3 (PDB:1XD3, yellow), and UCHL5 (PDB:4UEL, blue).

Figure 2: Rearrangement of the UCHL1 active site upon ubiquitin binding. A comparison of the active site triad (Cys90, His161, and Asp176) positions in the apo-enzyme (PDB: 2ETL, blue) and upon ubiquitin binding (PDB: 3KW5, grey), obtained by superposition of the two PDBs in ChimeraX, shows that ubiquitin binding triggers a reorganization of the side chains of these essential residues. The most notable shift was observed for His161, which moves to a position where it can impact the nucleophilicity of the active cysteine.

Figure 3. A schematic representation of UCHL1's various activities: In its monomeric form (Left) UCHL1 performs hydrolysis, cleaving the small extension from the C-terminus of ubiquitin through the active cysteine at position 90. Additionally, UCHL1 exhibits a high affinity for binding free mono-ubiquitin. According to a proposed model²⁰, the dimeric form of UCHL1 (Right) carries out an ATP-independent ligation activity, where the first unit binds to free mono-ubiquitin, and the second binds to the elongated ubiquitin C-terminus. The C90 cysteine cleaves this linkage, and the energy released produces di-ubiquitin. *This figure was created by Biorender.*

Data Availability Statement:

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

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UCHL1, beyond hydrolysis.

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UCHL1 is a neuron-enriched component of the ubiquitin-proteasome system. This review debates the biological relevance of its biochemical roles: limited DUB activity, potential ligase function, and mono-ubiquitin stabilization. We emphasize the need to clarify the mechanisms and identify natural substrates for each function to understand their role in neuronal ubiquitin signaling.

(Tal Kiri illustrated this image aided by Chat GPT Premium)

a.

149 E G Q C - - - - - R V D D K V N 159

154 E G Q T E - - - - - A P S I D E K V D 167

146 Q Q M F E F D T K - - - - T S A K E E D A 162

147 P E P R H L P E K Q N G L S A V R T M E A 167

b.

